

**An analysis of the relationship between the history of discrimination towards
Black Americans and the current issue of Systemic Racism in the United
States**

Author: Angie Mohamed (angie.mohamed22@sitechhs.com)

Mentors: Mamadou Barry (Director for FINX Research and Journalism)

Rehan Yazdani (Director for FINX Research and Journalism)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3983055

FINX Research and Journalism

August 11, 2020

Introduction

Annually, on the second Monday in October, the United States celebrates Columbus Day. And every year our social institutions ignore the truth of the events that have transpired since Columbus' "discovery." Christopher Columbus was a white, racist male whose opinions still reflect the attitude of some Americans. The federal holiday raises controversy every year over continuing to honor Columbus as a heroic figure. There are three main reasons of controversy based on Columbus encounter with indigenous people on his journey to the Americas, which includes: the forced conversion of Christianity on natives, the use of violence, and the spread of diseases that would all have negative long-term effects on these native people ("Why Columbus Day Causes Controversy" 2019). Columbus and the other Europeans viewed indigenous people as racially inferior and ultimately the extreme social construct of racism can be traced back to this time period.

Since the origins of racism and discrimination, it has increasingly become more ingrained in our society through our government, criminal justice system, education, health care, and other institutions. Racism has influenced people's perceptions and decisions for centuries and remains a prevalent issue for racial groups such as Black Americans, which includes people from Africa and Caribbean. This group is highly discriminated against and faces issues such as: unemployment, mistreatment, poor health care, racial profiling, red lining, unequal availability of resources, and several more. The deep-rooted issues of these groups is a symptom of systemic racism. Systemic racism is defined as the inequalities or discrimination based on racism embedded in society and within social institutions that disadvantages Black Americans (Yancey-Bragg 2020). Systemic racism contributes to the power of white supremacy (2020). It leads to disparities; for example despite blacks consisting of only 13% of the entire United States population, blacks make up almost half of the homeless population (2020). There is not only inequality in housing, but inequality exists in every facet of life.

To understand systemic racism, the history of the suppression of black people must be examined. In between 1525 to 1866, millions of African Americans were enslaved and sailed off to the United States. Slavery embedded racist views and attitudes towards African Americans and was the start of institutional or systemic racism. The fight against slavery began with the Civil War (1861-1865). Most people consider the end of slavery to be after the Civil War, however the official end of slavery was said to be in 1942. After the Civil War, Southern States used the criminal justice system to reinforce racial control, passing Black Codes and Jim Crow laws. These laws contradicted the 13th Amendment, which is known for abolishing involuntary servitude and slavery, except for a punishment of a crime ("Racial Disparity" 2020). This created a loophole in which states exploited when passing the Black Codes ("Racial Disparity" 2020). By arresting African Americans and giving them unfair and long sentences, states set up new

economic and labor systems, sharecropping and peonage- forced labor and convict leasing (2020). In violation of a Black Code, offenders had to pay fines, those who were unable to pay were forced into labor until they worked off the money, however these offenders were never released (2020). It wasn't until the Civil Rights Movement until African Americans were able to gain freedom. It's been only a few decades since Black Americans gained equal rights, and although they have these rights Blacks face discrimination daily. Black Americans face racial profiling, generational poverty, high incarceration rights, and more. Blacks have been discriminated against for centuries and social institutions reinforce this racism. These systems are based on a foundation that is flawed and prejudiced. People are often misinformed about the history of Black culture and the truth of why murders like George Floyd happen today, but America's history can help shed light on events and statistics of today. The history of discrimination towards Black Americans is correlated to the issues this group struggles with in the 21st century, such as discrimination with the social institutions of health care, the criminal justice system, and education.

Manuscript Body

The health care system in America may appear to be non-bias, but through the centuries Blacks have been mistreated and even today low income Black families suffer from lack of resources and treatment. It is common to think of medicine and health care to be neutral and driven solely by science, however medicine and the flawed health care system has continually discriminated against Black Americans. Take for instance, the Tuskegee Study of Untreated Syphilis in the Negro Male run by doctors from the U.S. Public Health Service (PHS) in 1932, before slavery was completely abolished (Nix 2019). For this experiment, six hundred black men were recruited and promised free health care (Nix 2019). Most of these men were sharecroppers who have never gone to the doctor, which ultimately shows the unavailability of healthcare to these men. For the study 399 men served as the experimental group and were given syphilis, while the other 201 served as the control group and were syphilis free (Nix 2019). This experiment was supposed to last 6 months, but instead lasted 40 years. Furthermore, PHS researchers told physicians to leave participants untreated and in 1947 when penicillin became the recommended treatment for syphilis, the infected men were only given placebos (aspirin and minerals) (Nix 2019). No effective care was given, although men died, went insane or blind, or experienced severe health problems from the untreated sexually transmitted disease (STD) (Nix 2019). In the mid-1960s, a PHS investigator, Peter Buxton, found out about the study and reported it as unethical to his superiors and a committee was created by PHS officials in response to his concerns (Nix 2019). The committee decided to continue the study with the objective of waiting until all participants died for autopsies to be done and data to be analyzed (Nix 2019).

But, Buxton passed on the story to a reporter and news broke about the study in July 1972, and the study was met with outrage and was forced to shut down (Nix 2019). By July 28 men were already dead from syphilis, 100 others were dead from related complications, at least 40 others contracted the disease, and the disease was passed to 19 children at birth (Nix 2019). Participants were black sharecroppers and were given syphilis without their knowledge, this study clearly raised several ethical issues such as racism, unfair subject selection, and no consent. This is not the only study that has discriminated against African Americans and has treated them with maleficence. Due to the Tuskegee experiment and others, many African Americans developed a mistrust for public health officials (Nix 2019). The fact that researchers targeted black sharecroppers shows the immense racism that existed in the 1900s.

Thereby, researchers and medical professionals have discriminated against African Americans and these acts of prejudice eventually led to more permanent consequences, such as high premature mortality rates. These high mortality rates are not due to a genetic flaw, but rather as a result of systematic racism in the health care system that was designed to disproportionately discriminate against people of color (Raj 2020). High mortality rates can be linked to several complications from the slavery hypertension hypothesis (Raj 2020). This hypothesis is linked to why African Americans have higher blood pressure as this theory argues that Africans inherited genes, through evolution, that affects their sodium levels (2020). Health disparities between different racial groups come from racism. Racism exists in every field of medicine, for instance glomerular filtration rate (GRF) (2020). GRF is a measurement clinicians use to assess renal functions and takes sex, age, weight, and race into account when estimated through equations (2020). This is problematic because GFR is closer to normal for a black person than their white counterpart, creating a low disease severity, which means blacks are diagnosed with end-stage renal disease much later than a white person and this leads to high mortality rates (2020). Why is race a factor of GFR? Race is used in equations to account for muscle mass, although there is no solid reason for why race may be related to muscle mass (Raj 2020). Furthermore, the problem of systemic racism can be seen with the COVID-19 pandemic.

During April 2020, New York City (NYC) was the epicenter of COVID-19 and just as some states were hit harder than others, so were some neighborhoods- specifically those of low-income (Wilson 2020). Comparing income data by Zip codes, the wealthiest 25% represented lower than 10% of the COVID-19 cases, while the bottom 25% of the average incomes accounted for 36% of all the cases (Wilson 2020). There is a growing amount of evidence, including a CDC examination in 99 countries, that show low-income, black communities are disproportionately being affected by the virus (Wilson 2020). In Michigan, not including Detroit, African Americans account for a third of the cases and 40% of deaths, but make up 14% of the population (2020). A possible reason for why black communities are

disproportionately suffering besides incidents of COVID-19 just being higher is that the availability of testing for marginal cases is lower because they have less access to testing (Wilson 2020). This yet again shows how the availability of resources is unequal for Black Americans and how they are not given access to resources and are therefore disadvantaged, just as the same population of people were disadvantaged in the Tuskegee study. This bias and inequity has become embedded in society. The Tuskegee Syphilis study may have expressed bias intentionally, but now institutions have been “programmed” to let black populations experience the downsides. This system was created to disadvantage black people, which can also be seen in the criminal justice system.

The criminal justice system today is based on the flawed system that was never changed after the Civil Rights Movement and Black Americans were granted their rights. It is a system that is made to benefit white people. For example take for instance the incarceration rates of Black Americans. Of the general population of America Black men comprise about 13% and 35% of those men are incarcerated (“Racial Disparity” 2020). Black women also make up 13% of the female U.S. population and comprise 44% of incarcerated women (“Racial Disparity” 2020). Additionally, looking at the stories of hundreds of young black lives, it appears that their fate is decided from the moment they are born. For example, PBS Frontline in 2001 filmed a documentary of four kids who faced the possibility of being tried as an adult at 17. Marquese was one of the young men in the film, he was 17 and was charged with 8 felonies (“Four Kids, Four Crimes” 2001). All these felonies were non-violent crimes and were ones dealing with property. Marquese was labeled a career criminal because he would rob people's homes and sometimes sell what he would find because he needed the money. These crimes are serious, however looking at his background, Marquese wasn't a completely troubled young man- he was misguided and can be rehabilitated. He was taught how to steal by his mother and his father was not in his life (“Four Kids, Four Crimes” 2001). His mom not only taught him to steal, but was constantly high on drugs, in and out of jail, as well as rehab facilities (“Four Kids, Four Crimes” 2001). He was sent to live with his aunt who owned a crack house and also served jail time (“Four Kids, Four Crimes” 2001). Marquese did not receive a formal education and did what his mother taught him how to do- steal (2001). He was charged with felonies, but how can he take full account of these crimes and be charged as an adult when the systems put into place failed him? Marquese ended up being sent to California Youth Authority (CYA) to serve out his sentence (2001). In the film there was also another young man, but he was white and grew up in an affluent community and attempted to murder his father (2001). It is clear he is a sociopath and there is no logical reason why he would attempt to kill his father, but the court allowed him to serve a very short sentence at county jail and while there he was able to attend college classes with a leg monitor, in which his parents paid for the classes (2001). This can all be connected

back to Black Codes and Jim Crow laws. This system clearly benefits white people. White landowners used to pay judges to give blacks high sentences, but today there is no need to pay them, the system inherently discriminates against blacks without intervention. Also, policies and laws that are passed only work to contribute to the problems. Take for instance, the violent crime control and law enforcement act of 1994, this implemented provisions that put more black people behind bars for longer periods of time (“Racial Disparity” 2020). It established three-strike laws, which means for an individual that already has 2 convictions for certain felonies, their third strike leads to automatic life sentences (“Racial Disparity” 2020). States that adopted this law saw an expansion in incarceration rates (“Racial Disparity” 2020). In 2019, 28 states still had this law (2020). Even in states who don't have this law, prosecutors and judges are able to recommend sentences based on the defendant's criminal history (2020). The result is that communities that are subject to harsher policing and prosecution receive more severe sentences (2020). Black communities suffer from the highest incarceration rates and worst sentences, which shows the inequality in the criminal justice system, but the problem runs deeper. There is something people in these communities are often missing- education.

The absence of education in the United States often leads not only to unemployment, but to the prosecution of drop-outs or those who were not given the opportunity to attend a high school. The education system is not only linked to the justice system, but is inherently biased and fails students the moment they walk in. Systemic racism in education is a root cause to a lot of the inequities people of color face. Furthermore, in the United States, students are taught about W.E.B Du Bois, Martin Luther King, Barack Obama, maybe Booker T. Washington, and they are often taught history through the white man's perspective. The accomplishments of black communities or simple exchanges often go unrecognized or ignored, however the gift of the Statue of Liberty from France is taught. The books that are read in school typically are written by white male authors with a few exceptions. There is a large misrepresentation and underrepresentation of Black history and culture, while white people are often given the credit, which displays the implicit bias of school curriculums.

The inequality present in the education system can be traced back to slavery, segregation of schools, the Supreme Court case Brown vs Board of Education, and the Little Rock Nine. Back when owning slaves was a social norm blacks were not given the right to education and were illiterate. After slavery was over and segregation was instilled in society blacks were still not given complete access to education. Schools were separated and were given less resources, poor facilities, and an unequal amount of funds. After the Supreme court case Brown v.s. The Board of Education in 1954 it was declared that was unconstitutional to establish racial segregation in the public school system. Since that decision there has been progress made in the

school system allowing more equality, but the problem of inequality was not erased. There are still several flaws in school districts such as inequitable funding and policing of students.

The funding system of the United States is severely unequal, disproportionately affecting low-income black communities. White, affluent school districts receive on average \$23 billion more than nonwhite school districts (Chatterji 2020). The lack of money impacts the quality of education students receive and hinders their future success (Partelow, Shapiro, McDaniels, & Brown 2018). The quality of a student's kindergarten to high school education affects their chances of dropping out, the university they attend, getting a job, and the amount of money they make (Partelow, Shapiro, McDaniels, & Brown 2018). Money in education matters, the more school districts spend the better students perform and the higher the graduation rates (Partelow, Shapiro, McDaniels, & Brown 2018). If a student does not have their high school diploma or GED, then it is hard to find a well-paying job to sustain themselves, as only 36% of jobs include people with a high diploma or less (Partelow, Shapiro, McDaniels, & Brown 2018). Also, those who have a college degree earn one million more, over a lifetime, than those who just have a high school degree (2018). Moreover, more funding and resources can reduce future crime rates and thereby allow less money to be needed towards the criminal justice system. Deviant behavior and how a person decides to behave beyond their family and peer groups, starts with school. Through increased funding, students can be provided with a means of success and different opportunities, as well as their needs met to accommodate their circumstances (Chatterji 2020). Additionally, examining the relationship between education and crime more closely a large factor is poverty. Those who often commit crimes are those living in poverty. If money spent per pupil annually increased 10% for public schooling, then it is predicted the annual incidence of adult poverty will drop 3.2% (Partelow, Shapiro, McDaniels, & Brown 2018). If more money in education leads to less poverty, then that may lead to a decrease in crime. The lack of funding for black communities is a pre-existing issue, as schools that accommodated people of color have been poorly funded since blacks started attending school in the late 1800s and were segregated. The inequality of the previous centuries continues to take root in several issues with social institutions today.

Another way schools have inherently affected black communities is through excessive policing and surveillance. After the 2018 school shooting in Parkland, Florida, twenty six states upgraded security and police officers that are on school campuses using about \$960 million to upgrade (Chatterji 2020). Although gun violence is a very important issue, there is no evidence to suggest that the threat of gun violence will effectively be addressed through increasing surveillance or policing (2020). The presence of police can also make students, more specifically Black students, feel less safe as they more likely will not be protected, but rather policed (2020). Data shows that 1.7 millions students attend schools with no counselors, 3 million with no

nurses, 6 million with no psychologists, and 10 million with no social workers, but these students go to school with police officers (2020). Predominantly black schools have a higher concentration of law enforcement officers than mental health staff (2020). This shows that not only are schools in black communities underfunded, but their funding is placed towards the ideology that black students need to be policed and monitored. According to the U.S. The Department of Education's Office for Civil Rights, not only are these students more policed and are subject to more contraband sweeps, arrests, integrations, but face higher rates of school disciplinary consequences like suspension and expulsion (Chatterji 2020). This data only reinforces that the progress that has been made since the Supreme Court case Brown vs Board of Education is insufficient and the present education system reflects the inequity of resources that have been provided to black communities since the late 1800s.

Conclusion

Thus, events and issues that have recently transcribed or are currently affecting Black Americans is a result of the long history of racism. The mistreatment and inequality of Black Americans in the 1600s are still present today, but disguised as systemic racism instead of outright slavery. Inequities exist in healthcare, the criminal justice system, and in education, as described in this paper and is clearly connected to the history of discrimination. The repercussions of mistreatment of Black Americans in the Tuskegee study, the loophole found in the 13th amendment that allowed white landowners to create sharecropping and convict lease, the segregation of Blacks in the schooling system all contribute to the accumulation of injustice that sets the foundation of several institutions in the United States. Consider this question: if a white male was asked how his life would be like if he switched lives with his black counterpart, would his answer be positive or negative? The answer to that question is not only based on the facts of systemic racism, but the way individuals were raised. Personal perceptions are influenced by the opinions of those around that person and how they are socialized. Every individual was socialized differently, but everyone was taught about racism, except through different lenses. The 21st century is in need of a new lens.

Works Cited

Chatterji, Roby. "Fighting Systemic Racism in K-12 Education: Helping Allies Move From the Keyboard to the School Board." *Center for American Progress*. 8 July 2020, <https://www.americanprogress.org/issues/education-k-12/news/2020/07/08/487386/fighting-systemic-racism-k-12-education-helping-allies-move-keyboard-school-board/>. Accessed on 8 August 2020.

"Four Kids, Four Crimes." *PBS.org*. 2001, <https://www.pbs.org/wgbh/pages/frontline/shows/juvenile/four/>. Accessed 8 August 2020.

Partelow, Lisette; Shapiro, Sarah; McDaniels, Abel; and Brown, Catherine. "Fixing Chronic Disinvestment in K-12 Schools." *Center for American Progress*. 20 Sept. 2018 <https://www.americanprogress.org/issues/education-k-12/reports/2018/09/20/457750/fixing-chronic-disinvestment-k-12-schools/>. Accessed 8 August 2020.

Nix, Elizabeth. "Tuskegee Experiment: The Infamous Syphilis Study." *History.com*. 29 July 2019, <https://www.history.com/news/the-infamous-40-year-tuskegee-study#:~:text=Known%20officially%20as%20the%20Tuskegee,known%20treatment%20for%20the%20disease.&text=Participants%20in%20the%20Tuskegee%20Syphilis%20Study>. Accessed on 8 August 2020.

“Racial Disparity.” *NACDL*. 2020, <https://www.nacdl.org/Landing/RacialDisparity>. Accessed on 8 August 2020.

Raj, Rhea. “Dissecting systemic health care in health care.” *KevinMD.com*. 18 June 2020, <https://www.kevinmd.com/blog/2020/06/dissecting-systemic-racism-in-health-care.html>. Accessed 8 August, 2020.

Wilson, Chris. “These Graphs Show How COVID-19 Is Ravaging New York City's Low-Income Neighborhoods.” *TIME*. 15 April 2020, <https://time.com/5821212/coronavirus-low-income-communities/>. Accessed on 8 August 2020.

“Why Columbus Day Causes Controversy.” *History.com*. 7 Oct. 2019, <https://www.history.com/news/columbus-day-controversy#:~:text=There%20are%20three%20main%20sources,effects%20on%20native%20people%20in>. Accessed on 8 August 2020.

Yancey-Bragg, N’dea. “What is systemic racism? Here's what it means and how you can help dismantle it.” *USA Today*. 19 June 2020, <https://www.usatoday.com/story/news/nation/2020/06/15/systemic-racism-what-does-mean/5343549002/>. Accessed on 8 August 2020.